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Line X Tester Analysis of Early Maturing Maize Inbred Lines for Yield and Secondary Traits

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Received Date: 9-Feb-2022

Accepted Date: 11-Mar-2022

Published Date: 30-Apr-2022

Abstract

Improving maize grain yield is a major objective of breeding programs in sub-Saharan Africa. This study was conducted to evaluate the potential of two multiple stress tolerant early maturing maize populations and for improving the cross performance of elite early maturing inbred lines. Five inbred lines were crossed with two maize populations to generate 10 testcrosses using a line x tester design. The 10 testcross hybrids, the two tester populations and two commercial hybrid checks were evaluated at two locations in Nigeria in a randomized complete block design. Trait means, combining ability effects and magnitude of heterosis expressed in the crosses were estimated. Differences ($P < 0.01$) in performance of testcrosses, and testcross \times environment interaction were observed for all measured traits. Inbred line VCML 10 combined better for grain yield with favourable ears per plant, root lodging and plant aspect ratings while TZEI 86 had the least desirable combining ability estimates for grain yield and secondary traits. Among the testcross hybrids, Early LN-W \times VCML10, EWLN-POP \times TZEEI-6 and EWLN-POP \times TZEI-86 were the top performing combinations for grain yield. Early LN-W was the better combiner of the two populations tested. Eight of the 10 testcrosses had higher yield advantage (9.24% - 79.08%) than the better performing commercial hybrid check. The tester populations can therefore serve as sources of favourable alleles for developing better performing hybrid varieties per se as well as for inbred line extraction.

Keywords: Early maturing, inbred, line \times tester, Maize, grain yield

Introduction

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is a major staple food crop in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). It is grown on approximately 35 million hectares by smallholder farmers in SSA, accounting for 20 % of the total global maize area (Badu-Apraku *et al.*, 2010; Malik *et al.*, 2005; Khalil *et al.*, 2011; FAOSTAT, 2013). Despite its significance as a major crop, average grain yields of less than 2 tons/ha are obtained in farmers' fields in SSA due to a combination of factors which include declining soil fertility, sub-optimal management practices and a combination of biotic and abiotic stresses (Shiferaw *et al.*, 2011).

Early maturing maize has contributed significantly to increased production and adoption of maize in WCA, especially in areas where the short duration of rainfall had limited maize cultivation (Boakyewaa, 2012). Early maturing maize varieties lengthen the opportunity corridor for planting maize, and are also more suitable for intercropping, because they compete less for moisture, light, and nutrients than later maturing varieties (CIMMYT, 2000).

Despite these cropping advantages, early maturing maize varieties are usually lower yielding than later maturing varieties. As costs of growing and harvesting maize are largely fixed, competitiveness of shorter duration crops in terms of grain yield and stress tolerance is crucial for its increased adoption. Information on grain yield and stress adaptation of maize genotypes could be obtained by estimating the amount and direction of heterosis, and the combining ability of genotypes in hybrid combinations (Ceyhan, 2003). Several methods

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have been used to study gene action and its effects in maize. These include the diallel and other factorial mating schemes such as the North Carolina Design I (NC 1), II (NC 2), III (NC 3) and the line x tester, mating schemes.

A line x tester mating design involves the crossing of a number of selections, lines, or clones to a common parent (tester) (Kempthorne, 1957). This It is used to estimate both general and specific combining ability effects. A desirable tester is defined by Matzinger (1953) as one that combines the greatest simplicity in use with the maximum information on performance to be expected from tested lines with respect to general and specific combining abilities. Numerous investigators found that the additive and the non-additive genetic effects (Kara 2001, Ashish and Singh 2002, Motawei 2006; Aly and Hassan 2011) have contributed significantly in the inheritance of grain yield and secondary traits. Information generated from line x tester analysis is an invaluable tool for resource allocation in old and emerging breeding programs especially in decision making involving planned crosses for new or introduced germplasm (Panhwar *et al.*, 2008). Two early maturing multiple stress tolerant and early maturing open pollinated varieties were developed at IITA Ibadan. So far, little or no information is available on their combining ability effects. Furthermore, these OPVs have not been crossed with the existing pool of elite IITA early and extra early maturing lines to determine their worth in improving and diversifying early maize gene pools in WCA. Therefore, keeping in view the above, this study was conducted with two objectives: (i) to estimate the general and specific combining ability of a group of early maturing maize germplasm for yield and secondary traits, (ii) identify superior hybrids combinations that can be utilized *per se* and (iii) determine the potential of the OPVs for future use in the breeding program.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site

Location of experimental sites

The study was conducted at Value Seed Limited's experimental stations located at Mokwa and Zaria, Nigeria in the 2020 cropping season. The Mokwa trial field (9°34'64"N, 5° 01'7"E) is situated in the Southern Guinea Savanna while the Zaria field (11°00'93"N, 7° 35'25"E) is situated in the Northern Guinea Savanna.

Genetic material and Experimental design

The parental germplasm used comprised of five maize inbred lines [(three from the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) Ibadan and two from the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Centre (CIMMYT)], and two open pollinated maize varieties from IITA Ibadan. All genotypes were of the early and very early maturing groups.

The mating design was a line x tester design. The inbred lines from IITA and CIMMYT were used as females and two open-pollinated varieties from IITA Ibadan served as males. Therefore, ten (10) experimental hybrids obtained from crossing the five inbred lines crossed to each of the two populations were evaluated alongside four checks namely; the two tester populations (EWLNPOP and Early LN-W) and two commercial hybrids viz. Sammaz 46 and Sammaz 47 of which three of the five inbred lines are parent lines. All genotypes studied were white-kernelled. The pedigree of the parent lines and check genotypes used for the study are shown below (Table 1).

The experiments were laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications in both locations. Plots consisted of single-rows, each 3 m long with 0.75 m spacing between rows and 0.25 m within rows. Two seeds were planted per hill and seedlings later thinned to one per hill three weeks after planting (WAP) to give a final plant population density of 53,333 plants/ha. Experimental fields in Mokwa and Zaria were planted on the 8th and 10th of August, 2020 respectively. Basal fertilizer application was carried out at 2WAP using NPK15:15:15 compound fertilizer at the rate of 30 kg each of N, P and K/ ha, while top-dressing

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was done at 6WAP using urea (46 % N) fertilizer at the rate of 60 kg N/ha, bringing the total amount of nitrogen applied to 90 kg N/ha.

Weeds were controlled by a pre-planting spray of glyphosate (N-(phosphonomethyl) glycine) at ten days before planting. A mixture of metolachlor ([2-methoxy-1-methylethyl) amino]oxo-acetic acid) plus atrazine (6-Chloro-N-ethyl-N#39;-(1-methylethyl)-1,3,5-triazine-2,4-diamine) was applied at planting at the rate of 1.6 kg a.i. ha⁻¹ for pre-emergence weed control. At 4WAP, Nicosulfuron (2-[(4,6-dimethoxypyrimidin-2-yl) carbamoylsulfamoyl]-N, N-dimethylpyridine-3-carboxamide) at the rate of 160 g a.i. ha⁻¹ was applied for post emergence weed control. Hand weeding was done where necessary. Rains ceased on the 10th and 4th of October in the experimental fields and most genotypes had not completed flowering and were therefore moisture stressed.

Data Collected

Agronomic data collected were days to anthesis, days to silking, plant height, plant aspect, husk cover rating, stalk and root lodging, ear aspect, number of ears per plant and grain yield. Days to 50% anthesis and days to 50% silking were the number of days from planting to when 50% of plants shed pollen and extrude silks. Anthesis-silking interval (ASI) was computed as the difference between days to 50% anthesis and days to 50% silking. Plant height was measured in centimeters (cm) on five competitive plants as distance from the ground level to the collar of the uppermost leaf. Plant aspect was scored on a scale of 1 to 9 based on overall plant appeal (plant and ear heights), uniformity of plants, disease and pest damage and lodging, with 1 = excellent plant type and 9 = poor plant type. Husk cover was rated per plot on a scale of 1-9 based on the tightness of the tips of the husks, where 1 represents long and tight tip, and 9 for very short and loose tip. Stalk lodging was measured by counting the number of plants that broke below the first ear per plot expressed as percentage of plant stand. Root lodging was estimated by counting the number of plants that lie completely flat on soil surface and/or are at angles less than 45° to the soil surface expressed as percentage of plant stand.

At harvest, ear aspect was rated per plot based on the neatness of ears and grain fill on the cobs on a scale of 1-9, with 1 representing clean and well-filled ears, and 9 for ears with scanty and rotten or damaged kernels. The number of ears per plant was estimated as the number of harvested ears divided by the number of plants in a plot. Field weight was measured as the weight of the de-husked maize cobs per plot in kg at harvest. Moisture content of grains at harvest was determined by threshing a sample of harvested cobs and testing for grain moisture content using a Dickey-John moisture meter.

Grain yield was calculated from the field weight, and adjusted to 14 % moisture content, i.e., Grain yield (kg/ha) = Field weight (kg)/area (m²) × (100-moisture)/86 × (10,000 × 0.80).

Statistical analysis

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) across environments for all data was performed using PROC GLM procedures in SAS computer package, version 9.2 following a linear model:

$$Y_{ijk} = \mu + r(e_k) + e_k + l_i + t_j + (l \times t)_{ij} + (l \times e)_{ik} + [(t \times e)_{jk} + (l \times t \times e)_{eijk}] + \epsilon_{ijk}$$

Y_{ijk} is measured trait of the genotype of ith line crossed to jth tester evaluated in r replications across k environments; μ is grand mean; r (e_k) is the effect of replication nested within the k environments; l and t represent average effects of lines and of testers, respectively, which is equivalent to GCA effects of lines and testers, respectively; l × t = line × tester interaction effects that is equivalent to the SCA effects of the crosses; e is the environmental main effects; l × e, t × e and l × t × e are the interactions of the lines, testers and the lines × testers with the environments, and e_{ijk} is the random experimental error. The hybrid component of variation

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was divided into variation attributable to Lines (females), Testers (males) and Line x Tester interaction. General and specific combining abilities for the studied traits were estimated according to Singh and Chaudhary (1985).

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Table 1. List of pedigree information of maize genotypes used in the study

Genotype	Name	Pedigree	Attribute	Origin	Source
Lines					
1	ENT 3	[M37W/ZM607#bF37sr-2-3sr-6-2-X]-8-2-X-1-BB-B-xP84c1 F27-4-3-3-B-1-B] F29-1-2-1-6 x [KILIMA ST94A]-30/MSV-03-2-10-B-1 B-B-xP84c1 F27-4-1-6-B-5-B]3-1-2-B/CML442]-1-1	Drought and Low nitrogen tolerant	CIMMYT	IITA
2	TZEEI 6	TZEE-W SR BC5 × 1368 STR S7 INB 100	Low nitrogen tolerant and Striga resistant	IITA	IITA
3	TZEI 65	TZE-W Pop×1368 STR S7 Inb 10	Low nitrogen tolerant and Striga resistant	IITA	IITA
4	TZEI 86	TZE-W Pop STR Co S6 Inbred 141-1-2	Low nitrogen tolerant and Striga resistant	IITA	IITA
5	VCML 10	CL106949	Drought and Low nitrogen tolerant	CIMMYT	CIMMYT
Testers					
6	Early LN-W	Early LN-W	Drought and Low nitrogen tolerant	IITA	IITA
7	EWLN-POP	EWLN-POP	Low nitrogen tolerant and Striga tolerant	IITA	IITA

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mean squares of combined analysis of variance for the derived testcrosses in both environments are presented in Table 2. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$ – $p < 0.01$) were observed among environments, crosses (with the exception of stalk lodging) and crosses x environment interaction (GEI) effects for all traits (Table 2). The significant mean squares indicate that the genotypes differed in trait performance in the two environments while significant cross x environment mean squares imply that the response patterns of the genotypes for these traits were influenced by environment. This is similar to the findings of Aly and Amer (2008), Aly *et al.* (2011) and Mousa and Aly (2012) who reported significant differences across experimental locations in maize.

In a similar study, Shiri *et al.* (2010), and Kustanto *et al.* (2012) also found non-significant differences for stalk lodging in maize, indicating that the expression of the trait is often environment dependent and can be conditioned by location effects such as effects of wind.

A further breakdown of the Crosses and Crosses x environment components of variation in the line x tester analysis showed that variation among Lines (GCA-female effect), and testers (GCA-male effect) were significant ($p < 0.05$) for all traits except stalk lodging. For the ten agronomic traits considered in this study, Line x Tester (female x male) interaction was significantly different for all the traits except for plant height, root lodging and ears per plant. This suggests that inbred lines may have different combining ability patterns and performed differently in crosses depending on type of tester used.

The importance of the interaction of the components of crosses with environment were more pronounced for lines than testers. All Environment x Line interaction effects were significant; five (of the ten interactions) were significant for Environment x Tester, and nine for Environment x Line x Tester interaction. Root lodging, ear aspect, ears per plant and grain yield were however significant for all three components of Crosses x Environments.

Significant Line or Tester x environment interactions suggest that there is significant variation in combining ability of the lines or testers in the different environments. these results corroborate with the findings of Chandel and Mankotia (2014) and Mosa (2010) who reported significant interaction for (L x E), (T x E) for grain yield and ear diameter and (L x T x E) for plant height and grain yield.

Estimates of GCA for agronomic traits of all the parent genotypes (5 lines and 2 testers) are presented in Table 3. Line VCML 10 had positive and significant GCA value for grain yield, whereas TZEI 86 had negative and significant GCA estimates for grain yield. Both positive and negative GCA effects in lines were reported in maize by several investigators Ahmad and Saleem (2003) and Shenawy *et al.* (2009) in line x tester designs. The high GCA value of VCML 10 indicates its superiority for favourable alleles influencing grain yield. Similar results of lines contributing to grain yield superiority of their crosses have been reported by El-Shenawy and Mosa (2005), Mosa (2010) and Mousa and Aly (2012).

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Table 2. Mean squares from the analysis of variance of agronomic of 10 testcross hybrids evaluated at Mokwa and Zaria, Nigeria in 2020 cropping season.

Source of Variation	Df	D POLL	DYSK	PLHT	PASP	HUSK	SL	RL	EASP	EPP	GYLD (t/ha)
Environment (Env.)	1	57.1**	99.51**	11251.45**	38.24**	51.19**	0.40**	0.88**	24.61**	0.276**	154.45**
Rep	4	1.27NS	2.23NS	240.43NS	0.03NS	0.42NS	0.22NS	0.54NS	0.23NS	0.003NS	1.9NS
Crosses	9	15.38**	13.57*	634.74**	1.8**	0.56**	0.11NS	0.22**	0.67*	0.005*	4.01**
Line	4	26.28**	19.36**	1322.49**	3.68**	0.94**	0.07NS	0.31**	0.89**	0.005*	6.68**
Tester	1	6.94**	5.29**	238.22**	0.33**	0.62**	0.01NS	0.48**	1.37**	0.018**	3.8**
Line × Tester	4	6.65**	9.94**	45.82NS	0.27*	0.2*	0.19**	0.07NS	0.27**	0.002NS	1.43**
Env. × Crosses	9	1.39**	2.08**	610.82**	1.61**	0.55**	0.15**	0.24**	0.76**	0.016**	4.36**
Env. × Line	4	0.89*	2.31*	1186.51**	3.36**	1.06**	0.16**	0.17**	1.03**	0.022**	7.98**
Env. × Tester	1	0.12NS	0.5NS	2.7NS	0.03NS	0.39**	0.01NS	0.22**	0.39**	0.028**	1.55**
Env. × Line × Tester	4	2.2**	2.25**	187.16**	0.26*	0.08NS	0.18**	0.31**	0.59**	0.008**	1.43**
Error	35	1.22	1.85	139.54	0.39	0.28	0.18	0.2	0.2	0.007	1.02

** , *; significance at 0.05 and 0.01, probability levels, respectively; NS = not significant; Df = degree of freedom; DPOLL = days to 50% pollen shed, DYSK = days to 50% silking, PLHT= plant height, PASP = plant aspect, HUSK= husk cover, RL = root lodging, SL = stalk lodging, EASP = ear aspect, EPP = ears per plant, GYLD = grain yield.

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Table 3. Estimates of general combining ability (GCA) effects of the 5 lines and 2 testers for agronomic traits measured in Mokwa and Zaria, Nigeria, 2020

Parent Genotypes	D POLL	DYSK	PLHT	PASP	HUSK	SL	RL	EASP	EPP	GYLD (t/ha)
Lines										
ENT 3	1.34*	1.72**	7.83*	-0.12	-0.22*	0.06*	0.00	-0.25**	0.01*	-0.29
TZEEI 6	-1.97**	-1.56**	0.19	0.41*	-0.22*	0.05*	0.20**	0.02	-0.02**	-0.28
TZEI 65	-1.05*	-1.06*	8.81*	-0.09	-0.30**	-0.12**	0.11*	-0.06	0.01	0.24
TZEI 86	0.28	0.28	-17.76**	0.57**	0.28**	-0.04	-0.05	0.44**	-0.02**	-0.81**
VCML 10	1.53**	0.82*	1.04*	-0.84**	0.28**	0.05*	-0.22**	-0.23*	0.02**	1.18**
S.E	1.34	1.15	9.47	0.50	0.25	0.07	0.15	0.25	0.02	0.67
Testers										
Early LN-W	0.39**	0.37**	2.13**	-0.09**	-0.15**	-0.01*	0.10**	-0.17**	0.02**	0.24*
EWLN-POP	-0.33*	-0.29*	-2.08**	0.06*	0.08*	0.01*	-0.09*	0.14*	-0.02*	-0.23*
S.E	0.34	0.30	2.01	0.08	0.10	0.02	0.09	0.15	0.02	0.25

** , * significance at 0.05 and 0.01, probability levels, respectively; S.E = standard error; DPOLL = days to 50% pollen shed, DYSK = days to 50% silking, PLHT= plant height, PASP = plant aspect, HUSK= husk cover, RL = root lodging, SL = stalk lodging, EASP = ear aspect, EPP = ears per plant, GYLD = grain yield.

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GCA estimates for number of ears per plant were positive and significant for lines ENT 3 and VCML 10, while estimates for TZEEI 6 and TZEI 86 were negative and significant. Lines with high GCA effects for number of ears per plant are suitable parents for hybrid formation (Asif *et al.*, 2007). Ears per plant which is a measure of prolificacy is an important trait in selection indices when breeding for stress (e.g., drought and low nitrogen) tolerance. Prolific varieties are also well suited to farming systems where crops are intercropped as they increase the number of harvestable ears and yield per ha higher especially under favourable conditions (Zeljko *et al.*, 2013). The direction of estimates for plant and ear aspects as well as flowering traits (DPOLL and DYSK) were similar for all the lines studied. VCML10 and ENT 3 were negative and significant for ear aspect and VCML10 for plant aspect. TZEI 86 was the only line with positive and significant ear aspect estimates while TZEEI 6 and TZEI 86 were positive and significant for plant aspect.

TZEEI 6 and TZEI 65 had negative and significant GCA estimates for DPOLL and DYSK while ENT 3 and VCML 10 had positive and significant effects for these same flowering traits. In effect, testcrosses involving TZEEI 6 and TZEI 65 have a tendency to flower earlier, while crosses with ENT 3 and VCML 10 were later maturing. GCA estimates for lines ENT 3 and TZEI 65 were positive and significant, while TZEI 86 was negative and significant, indicating that these lines have the tendency to increase or decrease plant heights of their testcross hybrids.

Three lines (ENT 3, TZEEI 6 and TZEI 65) had negative and significant effects for husk cover ratings while TZEI 86 and VCML 10 were positive and significant. The five lines showed variation in the direction of contribution for GCA for stalk lodging. TZEEI 6 was the only line with positive and significant GCA for root and stalk lodging while lines ENT, TZEI 65 and VCML 10 had a positive and a negative significant estimate for either root or stalk lodging. Positive GCA estimates for root and stalk lodging was observed for line TZEEI 6, thus indicating that crosses involving this line will be more predisposed to lodging.

GCA estimates for testers were significant for all values. Tester Early LN-W had desirable estimates for 6 of the 10 traits measured which were positive (desirable) for grain yield and ears per plant, and negative (desirable) for plant and ear aspects, husk cover and stalk lodging. EWLN-POP on the other hand although having negative (favorable) and significant GCA effects for earlier maturity and plant height and root lodging which are indeed desirable traits, had negative GCA estimates for grain yield and ears per plant and positive (undesirable) estimates for the four other traits and was the lesser performing tester in terms of its breeding value (Table 3).

Specific combining ability estimates for agronomic traits of the 10 testcrosses are shown in Table 4. Significant positive and negative SCA effects ($p \leq 0.05$) for grain yield were observed for EWLNPOP x TZEEI 6, EWLNPOP x TZEI 86 and Early LN-W x VCML 10. Crosses with negative and significant SCA effects ($p \leq 0.05$) for grain yield were Early LN-W x TZEEI 6, Early LN-Y x TZEI 86 and EWLN-POP x VCML 10.

Crosses with significant SCA effects for DPOLL in 6 of 7 instances also had significant SCA for DYSK. Two hybrids ELN-W x TZEEI 6 and EWLNPOP x VCML 10 had negative (desirable) and significant SCA effects for plant height and positive (undesirable) effects for ear aspect,

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Table 4. Estimates of specific combining ability effects (SCA) of line x tester crosses evaluated for grain yield and other traits for the testcross hybrids at Zaria and Mokwa, Nigeria in 2021

Testcrosses	DPLL	DYSK	PLHT	PASP	HUSK	SL	RL	EASP	EPP	GYLD (t/ha)
Early LN-W×ENT 3	1.08**	1.24**	-0.41	-0.03	0.19**	0.02	0.05*	-0.02	0.01	-0.17
EWLN-POP×ENT 3	-1.14**	1.32**	0.37	0.06	0.26**	-0.02	0.03	0.05	-0.01*	0.15
Early LN-W×TZEEI-6	-0.89**	0.87**	3.11**	0.17**	0.15**	0.18**	-0.02	0.26**	0.01**	-0.20*
EWLN-POP×TZEEI-6	0.83**	0.79*	3.07**	0.14**	-0.08*	0.18**	0.00	0.22**	0.01*	0.19*
Early LN-W×TZEI-65	-0.14	-0.54*	0.84	0.17**	0.07*	0.01	0.06*	0.01	0.02*	-0.08

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EWLN-POP×TZEI-65	0.08	0.46	-0.88	0.14**	0.00	-0.01	0.08*	0.03	0.02**	0.06
Early LN-W×TZEI-86	-0.47*	-0.70*	0.61	0.16**	0.15**	-0.07*	0.06*	0.01	0.01**	-0.20*
EWLN-POP×TZEI-86	0.42*	0.62*	-0.65	0.19**	-0.08*	0.07*	0.08*	0.03	0.01*	0.18*
Early LN-W×VCML10	0.28	0.67*	1.96**	-0.08*	-0.01	0.15**	0.10*	0.16**	-0.01*	0.61**
EWLN-POP×VCML10	-0.33	-0.75*	2.01**	0.11*	0.08*	0.15**	0.09*	0.20**	0.00	-0.63**
S.E SCA	0.67	0.82	1.76	0.14	0.12	0.12	0.07	0.13	0.01	0.31

******, * significance at 0.05 and 0.01, probability levels, respectively; SE = standard error; DPOLL = days to 50% pollen shed, DYSK = days to 50% silking, PLHT= plant height, PASP = plant aspect, HUSK= husk cover, RL = root lodging, SL = stalk lodging, EASP = ear aspect, EPP = ears per plant, GYLD = grain yield.

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while another two EWLN-POP x TZEEI 6 and Early LN-W x VCML 10 had positive effects (undesirable) for plant height and negative (desirable) effects for ear aspect, indicating that deviations from GCA estimates of plant height in these two testcrosses were accompanied by a reverse expression in ear aspect and vice versa. Plant aspect and HUSK had 8 significant SCA effects each (4 positive and 4 negative) and four of the crosses having PASP and HUSK estimates in the same direction indicating a relationship of both traits in desirability of the hybrid phenotypes. Significant SCA effects for SL and RL were observed in the same direction for two (Early LN-W x VCML 10 and EWLN-POP x VCML 10) of the 10 testcrosses. Two crosses (Early LN-W x TZEI 86 and EWLN-POP x TZEI 86) had either a positive or negative SCA for SL and RL respectively, while 2 and 3 other crosses had significant SL and RL effects.

Specific combining ability effects for EPP were positive and significant for 3, and negative and significant for 5 testcrosses. Four of the eight testcrosses *viz.* Early LN-W x TZEEI 6, EWLN-POP x TZEEI 6, Early LN-W x TZEI 86 and EWLN-POP x TZEI 86 had significant EPP effects in the same direction with SCA effect for grain yield.

Highly significant SCA effects of the crosses indicate that significant deviation from what would have been predicted based on their parental performances. Crosses with highly positive and significant estimates of SCA effect indicate heterosis and parent lines of such lines could be selected for combining ability studies in maize improvement. The results of the current study are in agreement with the findings of Shushay *et al.* (2013), Shams *et al.* (2010) and Iqbal *et al.* (2007) who reported significant to highly significant level of SCA effects for grain yield and secondary traits in maize.

Comparisons between trait means of testcrosses and standard checks evaluated in Mokwa and Zaria in 2020 growing season is presented on Table 5. Standard heterosis/grain yield advantage was estimated in comparison to the commercial checks (TZEI 60×TZEI 86 and ENT 3×TZEI 65). All testcrosses showed grain yield superiority over the first check (TZEI 60×TZEI 86), ranging from 34.91% (EWLN-POP×TZEI-86) to 154.48 (ELN-W×VCML10). Standard heterosis estimated in comparison to commercial check 2 (ENT 3×TZEI 65) ranged from -5.06 (EWLN-POP×TZEI 86) to 79.08 (ELN-W×VCML 10). Result revealed that following hybrids ELN-W×TZEI-86 (79.08), ELN-W×ENT 3 (31.67), EWLN-POP×TZEI-86 (29.46), ELN-W×TZEEI-6 (22.05), ELN-W×VCML10 (13.51), EWLN-POP×VCML10 (12.97), EWLN-POP×TZEI-65 (10.61) and ELN-W×TZEI-65 (9.24) outperformed the better performing commercial check ENT 3×TZEI 65. Only two testcrosses (EWLN-POP×ENT 3 (-5.06) and EWLN-POP×TZEEI-6 (-2.5) performed lower than the better performing commercial check ENT 3×TZEI 65 (Abrha *et al.*, 2013; Mesenbet *et al.*, 2016; Abebe *et al.*, 2020) in their study identified maize testcrosses outperforming standard hybrid checks for grain yield and secondary

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Table 5. Means of agronomic traits and grain yield standard heterosis estimates of testcrosses vs hybrid checks averaged over two environments (Mokwa and Zaria) in 2020 growing season.

Genotypes	DPOLL	DYSK	PLHT	PASP	HUSK	SL	RL	EASP	EPP	GYLD	Standard Heterosis (GYLD)	
											TZEI 60×TZEI 86	ENT 3×TZEI 65
Testcrosses												
Early LN-W×ENT 3	56.78	58.21	160.80	4.27	3.49	0.19	0.28	4.45	0.97	3.90	61.30	13.51
EWLN-POP×ENT 3	53.83	55.00	157.37	4.50	4.17	0.17	0.17	4.83	0.92	3.75	55.23	9.24
Early LN-W×TZEEI-6	51.50	52.83	150.47	5.00	3.83	0.33	0.50	5.00	0.92	3.88	60.53	12.97
EWLN-POP×TZEEI-6	52.50	53.83	152.43	4.83	3.83	0.00	0.33	4.83	0.91	3.80	57.17	10.61
Early LN-W×TZEI-65	53.17	53.67	163.03	4.50	3.67	0.00	0.50	4.67	0.98	4.52	87.11	31.67
EWLN-POP×TZEI-65	52.67	54.00	157.10	4.33	3.83	0.00	0.17	5.00	0.90	4.19	73.43	22.05
Early LN-W×TZEI-86	54.17	54.83	136.23	4.83	4.33	0.00	0.33	5.17	0.92	3.35	38.55	-2.50
EWLN-POP×TZEI-86	54.33	55.50	130.77	5.33	4.33	0.17	0.00	5.50	0.90	3.26	34.91	-5.06
Early LN-W×VCML10	56.17	56.75	156.38	3.50	4.17	0.00	0.00	4.33	0.97	6.15	154.48	79.08
EWLN-POP×VCML10	54.83	54.67	148.20	3.83	4.50	0.33	0.00	5.00	0.94	4.44	83.96	29.46
Mean												
Checks												
TZEI 60×TZEI 86	56.83	57.50	135.13	5.33	4.00	0.00	0.00	5.17	0.90	2.42		
ENT 3×TZEI 65	55.33	56.83	150.03	4.00	3.67	0.00	0.17	5.00	0.89	3.43		
Mean	56.08	57.17	142.58	4.67	3.83	0.00	0.08	5.08	0.90	2.92		
Grand Mean	54.34	55.30	149.83	4.52	3.99	0.10	0.20	4.91	0.93	3.92		
LSD_{0.05}	1.28	1.46	10.0	0.54	0.57	0.33	0.34	0.3	0.08	0.76		

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trait, suggesting that they possess favourable alleles for inbred line extraction, this is an important tool to decide whether the hybrid is selected for promotion or not.

Conclusion

Considerable variability for genotypic performance in the two environments was observed in this study. Significant GCA estimates of lines and testers, as well as significant SCA effects of crosses for grain yield and secondary traits indicate the possibility of developing desirable combinations through planned crosses of inbred lines with desirable traits of interest. The lines VCML 10 and TZEI 65 were best general combiners for grain yield and secondary traits and show potential for improving grain yield. The crosses Early LN-W×VCML 10, Early LN-W× TZEI 65 and VCML10, EWLN-POP× VCML 10 could be utilized as top cross hybrids *per se* and should be further evaluated in multi-location trials. Both testers possess useful alleles for improving the cross performance of the elite inbred lines which was evidenced by the grain yield superiority of most testcrosses over the commercial single cross hybrid checks, implying that they are suitable candidates for line extraction. Of the two testers, Early LN-W was the better combiner for grain yield and ears per plant, plant and ear appeal, and could be useful in developing better performing early maturing varieties for the guinea Savanna agro-ecology of WCA.

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